

BRICOLAGE BUILDING: FOUR STRATEGIES TO RECONSTRUCT EXTRA-LEGAL SETTLEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Already, over a billion people live in cities that are built on land illegally acquired with unsanctioned means. Current studies indicate that this figure will only grow in the coming years (Mahabir, 2016) (Figure 1). Almost every aspect of these extra-legal settlement will be realized without the formal input of politicians, policy-makers, planners, architects and engineers.

It is important to note that this professional marginalization is not due to a lack of relevant expertise or desire to help. Rather, it is because the frameworks supporting most of these professionals are misaligned from the practices used in these extra-legal communities. Whereas architects and engineers, in training and practice, embrace a patronage-driven, linear, and relatively segmented approach to projects, extra-legal communities are realized much more fluidly, allowing them to be built at a rate far outpacing the supportive capacity of the governing authorities.

To impact this reality, those who are responsible for the design and construction of our built environments must recalibrate their approach to more closely align with this reality. This paper will delineate four strategies to this end.

KEYWORDS: extra-legal settlement; bricolage; socially-responsive design

Figure 1: Extra-legal settlements, such as the one shown above, currently house over a billion people, representing one of the most common urban conditions on the planet (John Miller, 2018)

PART ONE: UNDERSTANDING LEGAL PRACTICES

Those responsible for the design and construction of legal settlements are predisposed toward the realization of large and complex works. Although these approaches offer value when deployed in these contexts, they can become problematic when deployed within extra-legal settlements (Shall, 2021). To understand the nature of these professions, and how those practicing therein came to be so misaligned with the built environments currently housing over a billion people, one can look to the initial formation of these fields. For example, looking into the fields of both engineering and architecture, one quickly recognizes that both professions owe their existence to their ability to differentiate the efforts of those within these fields of practice from the works offered by master-masons and other construction experts. Historian L. D. Ettlinger argues that, for the architect, this professional separation can be traced back to the 15th century, when Brunelleschi designed the dome at Santa Maria del Fiore (Ettlinger, 1977). The professional independence of the engineer likely occurred much earlier, due to the field's hold over rare and widely-valued expertise. Nevertheless, regardless of timing, both professions only exist because the newly-minted professionals were able to realize larger and more complex work than what the other trades could offer. This linked both professions to those who could afford and find value in such complex, and expensive, undertakings (Cuff, 1998). As this identity matured over time, both professions sought to capitalize upon their relationship with society's most powerful actors, so as to gain more stable professional standing. This effort took many forms, including advocating for legislative support in order to mandate certain educational formats (via accreditation) and establishing approved training protocols (via licensure). Additionally, both professions lobbied, successfully, for a series of laws that required all projects of a specified size and complexity to be designed and certified by one, or both, professionals.

Today, this alignment between those who design legal settlements and those who profit most from them is quite profound. In education, training and practice, engineers, architects and other design professionals have accepted the needs of their powerful clients as their own. This is manifest in the manner in which these professionals train themselves, conduct business and evaluate success. For example, in order to re-affirm the value of the field, both the engineer and architect had to provide work that clearly supported the goals of their privileged clientele. This need encouraged the architect and engineer to create evaluation structures that emphasized measurable, consistent and quantifiable concerns. Correspondingly, matters such as the optimization of structure or the efficacious use of environmental resources have become central to the understanding of excellence in both fields, whereas ideals related to less-measurable concerns are of much lesser consequence. There is, however, one notable exception to this rule: if the professional is able generate symbolic capital through the work, through which the patron might reaffirm their status and predilections, then the pursuit of less measurable ends is encouraged (Stevens, 1998). Although a handful of professionals have been able to use this loophole to pursue ideals in service to communities outside their historic client base, this situation remains the exception, not the rule. The vast majority of those who design legal settlements continue to pursue means, materials and approaches that are directly tied to the concerns their long-time patrons.

PART TWO: UNDERSTANDING EXTRA-LEGAL PRACTICES

Although this arrangement, and the attendant professional frameworks, have obvious value for the professional, their clients, and the legal settlements thereby realized, it holds less value when deployed within extra-legal settlements, which are fundamentally misaligned with these biases. To thrive within the extra-legal settlement demands a much nimbler

professional structure that is capable of thriving within the vicissitudes of this unique urban environment. For within the extra-legal settlement, the residents rarely have jurisdiction over their context. Thus, the conditions they encounter can often change unexpectedly, and without warning. This can cause even the most well-considered work, at least as measured by the values and structures previously described, to have a negative impact when imposed upon this setting. To address this, those who wish to work within the extra-legal settlement must come to terms with the unique characteristics of these settings. They must also recognize how their personal and professional inclinations are fundamentally misaligned with them.

The first, and most obvious, moment of misalignment is related to the largely hierarchical support structure for the professional, which is quite different than the heterarchical arrangements often found within extra-legal settlements. As previously outlined, those who design legal settlements are, through training, accreditation and licensure, uniquely equipped to realize large, complex works. Although extra-legal communities could certainly be helped by projects of this scale, the manner in which this work must be realized within these settings is quite different from how the architect and engineer are trained to achieve such monumentality. Returning to the roots of the fields in question: in patronage-based models of practice, the client is the initiator and funder of the entire design and construction effort. This establishes a strong hierarchy of values within the work, based upon a single point of review and approval. This limits the speed at which projects can be realized. This is in sharp contrast with the viral manner in which extra-legal settlements are built, which allows these communities to propagate at a scale and speed that far exceeds the ability of any single actor, private or public, to properly support (Anand and Parussini, 2017). As a result, when patronage-based approaches are deployed within extra-legal settlements, the resulting projects can have an uneven impact: improving the lives of some, while leaving others largely unimpacted. This uneven development strategy encourages those living in the unimproved regions to move into the communities which received assistance. This increases the density of the newly-improved sector beyond what can be supported by the newly-installed work, causing the community to become arguably worse off than if the work had never been completed.¹ Another problem with the deployment of normative, hierarchical structures within extra-legal settlements are the highly segmented and largely linear design process such structures encourage. This type of structure, although ideal when operating within settlements that are governed by laws requiring multiple stages of review and approval of any act of construction, is much too time-intensive for the extra-legal settlement.² Those who build extra-legal communities employ a much less linear and segmented construction process, with individual residents often functioning as patron, user, designer and contractor. This allows each work of the citizen-designer to seamlessly integrate into a massive grassroots effort, wherein each member of the community can contribute to the work of the whole. The pace at which the resulting development is realized is remarkably swift, far outpacing the design-then-review-then-construction process favored within legal settlements. As a result, by the time the professional, using a patronage-based model of practice, realizes one housing project hundreds of other homes will have already been built by the community, without approval or support (Thieme & Kovacs, 2015, p. 1).

The second moment of misalignment is a by-product of the largely mono-directional manner by which design intent is communicated when building within legal settlements, which conflicts with the multi-directional manner of sharing insight favored within extra-legal settlements. As described earlier, within patronage-based models of project development the client sets the agenda, which is then executed in a slow, deliberate process of project

realization. At each stage, from client to professional to sub-professional to contractor to sub-contractor, the wisdom of the project is clearly described and recorded. The documents that result establish legally-binding approaches to the work, to which all parties are beholden. Any digression from this approach can be viewed as a breach of contract. Although this approach is quite good at providing a predictable outcome that has been systematically verified by those invited into the process, it is also a process ripe for exploitation when used in extra-legal settlements. This is due to the fact that within this process, the values guiding the work, and determining its success, are communicated hierarchically. This creates a game of telephone, wherein each party may have knowledge of their part in the process, and some measure of understanding about those elements immediately impacting their work, but very little understanding about the variables informing parameters outside their purview. This situation can cause those designing the work to be somewhat removed from the initial vision for it, as well as the thinking behind how the work will be executed. Those constructing the project have even less direct knowledge of the initial vision, but a bit more about the approach to construction. And those using it have very little knowledge of the intent of the work, the wisdom behind the design or the thought undergirding its production. Within such an arrangement, it is altogether too easy for resources to be misappropriated or inefficiently deployed – an opportunity that is often exploited for personal gain.³

The third moment of misalignment is linked to the fact that the communication pattern described above works in inverse as well. This situation can isolate the parties sponsoring the work from the perspective of those who will one day use it, creating projects that are unable to thrive within the rigors of the extra-legal settlement for two reasons. Firstly, work executed in this manner lacks the capacity to incorporate local knowledge or leverage unanticipated or idiosyncratic circumstances (UN-Habitat, 2015, p. 3). The patron and design professional, who are often divorced from the extra-legal context have no knowledge of the clever approaches already deployed by the community. Thus, this wisdom cannot be leveraged to the benefit of the designed response. They also have little knowledge of the current circumstances within the settlement, which are ever-changing. For example, within extra-legal communities residents will often have to address multiple needs using a single address: the structure of the home is also used as a drying rack for clothes and vessel to cook dinner can also provide a means for bathing children. In the extra-legal community, providing access to education, sanitation, shelter and other resources are viewed as an integrated set of concerns, necessary for the better living of life. Thus, they are generally addressed through skillfully overlapped approaches. In contrast, the architect and engineer are trained to deploy solutions to specific problems, as established by their client. Any deviation from this set of concerns is regarded as a costly digression and a misallocation of resources. This compels the professional to focus upon technocratic solutions that successfully answer the established project scope, as defined by the patron, while studiously ignoring the potentially beneficial effect of overlapping other concerns.⁴ Secondly, the utilization of processes designed for legal settlements within extra-legal communities will generally cause the work to become divorced from its context, and viewed by the members of the community as an imposition. Correspondingly, instead of being placed in a situation wherein the work might be surrounded by people who are vested in its success, it is surrounded by skeptics. This skepticism is only reaffirmed by the nature of the work itself, which will generally be built using materials and componentry more aligned with the professional's preferred means and materials, all of which are intended to serve the process described earlier, rather than the means of the community. This disenfranchises the members of the community, rendering these citizen-designers incapable of supporting, through acts of upkeep or maintenance, the offered work. This approach also breeds continued dependency on outside support, as the

offered means make the residents incapable of building upon the effort using internal resources.⁵ This is not an inconsequential mistake, as the only way to keep pace with the viral propagation of these communities, and to offer effective assistance, is to empower those who live within them to build them well, without external support.

PART THREE: HYBRIDIZED PRACTICES

To enable those living in extra-legal settlements to rebuild their communities requires a different approach, rooted upon materials, means and methods common to this distinctive settlement type. As extra-legal settlements are generally built using scavenged materials, common tools and accessible techniques, this mandate typically forces the designer to ground their work upon these means. And, if these elements are to be refined, they must be refined in accordance with local wisdom, based upon tested knowledge and direct engagement. It is important to note that within the extra-legal settlement this pattern of engagement is true for not only matters related to the material practice of building, but the manner in which all elements of the built environment are realized. In this context, water is not something provided by an assumed connection to the civic grid. Rather such connections are generally created through a series of local negotiations with citizens who happen to live next to a hydrant, water line, or other water outlet – an infrastructure of support that has been refined over time through direct, localized testing and development. Although not strictly legal, this approach allows the residents of the extra-legal community to obtain these resources at a much modest cost. In a similar vein, the resident-builders who operate in these communities construct their work based upon a network of virally-propagated wisdom (Davis, 2006). Working within such an effective, localized network, the residents of extra-legal settlements have little incentive to create approaches that would require rigid hierarchies or isolating practices. After all, in many ways, their entire settlement exists because those who built it did so in defiance of such hierarchies and structures (Theime and Kovacs, 2015).

In thinking and practice, these citizen-builders function like bricoleurs (Shall, 2018). And within their seemingly rudimentary approach lie the clues to a more efficacious professional strategy.

Strategy One: Establish Resources

The first, and most important, shift needed in order to translate normative professional practices into those more suited to the extra-legal settlement is to ground the entire design and construction process upon the means and materials that are at-hand, as is done within the community. Although simple in concept, this mandate can become frustratingly difficult to execute effectively. This is because design is an inherently future-oriented exercise – a projection of how life might be lived. Thus, to properly ground a design response on whatever means are at hand requires that the evaluation of resources be based as much on potential as the parameters of the current work. For example, every material and tool embraced by the design must not only be readily available today, but have a high probability of being available, and useful, in the future. While this is unquestionably a complicated endeavor, the establishment of this bank of resources is made somewhat simpler by having a clear point of departure: scavenged materials that can be acquired for free, deployed using common tools and require little expertise or training to refine, install or maintain.

A small project in Port Elizabeth, South Africa, completed during the summer of 2019, illustrates how this principal might be manifest. This work, which was designed and constructed by a team of eleven students, faculty and professionals, centered upon the design

and construction an event- and maker-space, in collaboration with local partners. Now completed, this work has provided the local community with a physical space to store tools, organize and refine materials and construct future work. Just as importantly, the makerspace provides the community with a proof of concept, clearly demonstrating the value and potential of creatively reusing found objects in the construction of much-needed work. By completing this work in only ten days, with a small, relatively unskilled team and a budget of only \$1500, the completed project can operate as an inspirational blueprint. For it is through these limits that the offered work can shift from an inaccessible, and tantalizing, one-off to a blueprint through which the community might realize new works for years to come (Figure 2).

Figure 2: *In realizing this work in South Africa, the designers worked as bricoleurs, developing a community makerspace using only common tools and reclaimed materials. The resulting project, which cost less than \$1500, has successfully changed the manner in which new projects are developed within this community. (International Design Clinic, 2019)*

It is important to note that none of this would have been possible if the design effort did not begin with the establishment a resource library, instead of the analysis of the site or program, the iterative development of formal design strategies or other, more traditional starting points. Instead, the work began with the gathering and careful cataloguing of resources, using two tactics. One part of the design team used direct engagements with the context, travelling the areas around the project site in order to seek out free or reclaimed materials from recycling centers, businesses, community partners and other local assets. Within their search, they gave priority to materials and components that were commonly available and had obvious utility, both now and in the future. Whenever this group uncovered such a resource, they carefully measured and documented it. This information was then sent to the rest of the team, who digitized it. As this digital archive developed, this team began to use their digital tools to test the utility of each piece, giving acute attention to common, performative assets such as structural capacity, durability, and water-tightness.

Strategy TWO: Expand the Resource Library

Returning to the manner in which extra-legal settlements operate, once the initial inventory of resources is gathered and assessed, the citizen-designer, like the bricoleur, attempts to expand this material base by applying the gathered means in the realization of a project. Although any project could suffice, a shrewd bricoleur will generally choose an architectural endeavor that responds directly to the most critical and persistent conditions faced by the community. Once this case study is selected, those designing the work will attempt to realize all aspect of the proposed project without adding any new resources. This exercise serves two purposes. First, if the citizen-designers are successful, then they will have proven that their library is capable of realizing structures of some utility, an obvious asset to the residents of said community and a positive indicator for future development. Second, this effort will establish a value structure within the library. Components and materials that are uniquely capable of meeting common needs will be assigned great value, whereas resources that hold properties that are either routinely offered or are incapable of meeting common needs will be given less worth. In some contexts, this can result in components offering great durability being highly valued. In others, structural capacity may be a rarer attribute, and a more pressing concern. Either way, in performing this audit, the citizen-designer has established a hierarchy of means based upon persistent, local conditions, which will allow them, and their partners, to become more-informed scavengers, designers, and builders.

Returning to the work in South Africa, this principal was manifest in both the digital and physical resource library. Digitally, once the group assigned to build the archive had a substantial inventory, they ran two tests. The first, which was performed using software designed for building information modeling (Revit), tested various structural approaches for the project. Through these simulations, it was confirmed that the accumulated inventory of large metal panels, discovered within an Isuzu assembly plant during the scavenging phase of the effort, had the precision and structural capacity to become the main framing element for the project's flooring and walls. This team then conducted research to determine the availability of this resource, concluding that it was, and would be, widely available for free, on-hand whenever new engines arrived to the plant. Armed with this knowledge, both groups focused their efforts on this component. The digital archivists tested these panels against the programmatic needs of the work, developing an initial form and structural approach for the project. They also, using a software platform capable of modeling highly-detailed componentry (Rhino), tested various methods by which these panels might be assembled together, or joined with other componentry. The group operating on the site then added to this information using direct experiments: lifting the components to determine the difficulty posed by its size and weight to future construction efforts, setting them between supports and then adding weight to determine deflection, and making detailed observations as to the general durability of the objects. They also tested how to connect and mount these panels to one another, and the other key components in the work. These tests revealed critical deficiencies within the elements, which prompted this team to evolve these assets, as will be described in the next section. In this manner, digital and physical simulations combined to generate a field-tested archive that could serve as the grounds for not only this project, but future work as well.

Strategy THREE: Evolve Resource Library

The third shift required to generate work within extra-legal settlements is addressing the various shortcomings in both individual resources and the entire library that were revealed through the initial design and construction effort. With each unmet need, questions surface. Can the unfulfilled demands of the project be addressed through the evolution of an already

found resource? Or is a new, scavenged material required? Or is it necessary to purchase a resource in order to unlock the potential held by a more common, inexpensive material? To answer these questions, the professional can deploy both digital and physical simulations in coordinated fashion. Digital tools, which lend themselves to acts of simulation and the testing of known, measurable concerns - site parameters, gravity, solar infiltration – are quite good at addressing questions related to massing, orientation and location. Physical tools, which have an incredible faculty to test material concerns, are adept at addressing questions related to material assembly and detailing. Ideally, however, these tools operate symbiotically. For example, the digital simulation might uncover a potential asset that simply requires a few manipulations to perform as needed. This hypothesis can then be quickly tested on-site to see whether or not the manipulation is as straightforward as anticipated. Conversely, the physical simulation might reveal that a material can be made more durable or stronger by combining it with a different component – a hypothesis that is then tested digitally to see if this answers the demands of the project. Either way, as each hypothetical is tested and verified, the assessment prompts an evolution of both the componentry and library. This process can then be repeated until an approach to the initial case study project is finalized and all gaps within the library revealed and resolved.

Figure 3: Using laminated wood scrap for the roof structure reserved more valued materials for other structures and uses. (International Design Clinic, 2019)

Within the makerspace project in South Africa, this principle prompted the design team to address several gaps within the project and library. One such address was revealed when attempting to design the spanning members for the roof, which, due to the project's minimum program area and the size of the structure componentry for the floor and walls (a spacing established by the aforementioned metal panels), was much too large to be spanned by any of the assembled means. To address this, the team once again used both digital and physical tools. The digital archivists revisited their library to see if any of the larger assets might be strengthened to achieve the requisite load capacity or if any of the of smaller components might be easily combined to achieve the require span. Simultaneously, the on-site team directly tested some of the underutilized resources they had gathered to understand if these assets might be manipulated to create the roof structure. Through these experiments, the

team discovered that wood scraps, which had been accumulated as they were pulled from the steel of the reclaimed palettes, could be laminated together to form beams of sufficient size and strength. Armed with this hypothetical, a small group was sent to use this new technique in order to produce the necessary elements. Aside from addressing a significant gap within the project, this evolution of a free, under-utilized material eliminated the need to purchase wood for other structural elements. (Figure 3) Correspondingly, since the completion of the first work in 2019, this specific innovation has been used by the local community to realize several new projects, resulting in a cost savings of over 25% in each case. This has allowed the community, through incorporation of this single innovation, to complete five projects for the cost of four, resulting in the construction of more schools, clinics and other much-needed projects by local citizens for the same financial and environmental cost.

Strategy FOUR: Deploy Resource Library

Once the library has been proven to offer sufficient means to realize the first work, the professional can begin the build. However, as they do so, they must remember that the point of this effort is not the project at hand. Rather, the main purpose of the current construction is the continued evolution of the resource library, and the community's understanding of it. As such, at this stage of the effort the digital library plays a supportive role, responding to the questions posed by the physical execution of the work. The physical tools, which are much more accessible to the members of the community, now drive the conversation, providing more immediate insight through not only the completion of the structure, but the myriad experiments that are required to achieve this end. Tests to assess strategies for assembly, detailing, and finishing are conducted simultaneous to the build, each offering insight and questions to the other. And both serving to invent new strategies to allow for the expanded deployment of common materials or the incorporation of new or evolved assets.

Figure 4: Design attention was placed in service of common, scavenged means in order to maximize the value of pre-constrained means. (International Design Clinic, 2019)

Within the South African makerspace, this principle was deployed to answer myriad questions, including how to best join structural components to the cladding, how to pivot or slide the large walls of the structure in order to allow for larger group gatherings, and how to articulate the flooring. However, the most vexing concern addressed through this deployment once again involved the span of the roof and the attendant need to create purlins to span the distance between the laminated wood beams described earlier. Previous tests had revealed that glue lamination was too time-consuming for the number of purlins required and metal too resource intensive. So the team conducted a new series of test, eventually discovering that

a simple mechanical fastener could be used to allow some of the longer segments of wood scrap – a readily available asset - to serve the purpose. Inspired by the joinery of Thorncrowne Chapel by architect E. Fay Jones, this mechanical connection introduced a regimented and expressive joint to the project that met this need without the infusion of additional resources, unique tools or complex processes – assets that continue to be deployed in projects by local community members. (Figure 4)

CONCLUSION

If established in this manner, then the completed work will naturally provide a powerful testimony to the value of not only its design approach, but the library of resources upon which this approach is founded. As this testimony is shared with others, new opportunities will emerge: invitations for new partnerships, bids to create new work, and donations of new resources. Each of these opportunities, if conducted in the manner described above, offers the chance to expand and evolve the library until it can begin to spawn new versions of itself. This is already happening in South Africa, where those responsible for the first work are currently building homes, clinics and schools based upon this project. (Figure 5) As these citizen-designers continue to build upon the initial work, it will likely become possible to support an even more viral propagation of the growing movement – a promise that will be pursued when a fourth team returns to South Africa in 2022 to continue the collaborative development of work with local citizens.

Figure 5: This residence, completed one year after the Community Makerspace in Figure 2, was designed and constructed without any support from the architects responsible for the initial work. Nevertheless, it is strongly influenced by it, borrowing many approaches to achieve greater spans and more durable results at a lower cost. (Kevin Kimwelle, Indalo World, 2021)

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No data was assembled for the production of this paper.

¹ In 2009, the Indian government proposed the creation of an urban investment strategy in order to create a “slum-free India” in five years. In 2011, while this remarkable housing plan was still very much in development, a study revealed that not only would these efforts not eliminate slums within the country, but it would cause them to grow, as the proposed improvements would increase the pace of in-migration to the renovated communities, causing overcrowding and the eventual deterioration of the conditions the program set out to improve (Marx, Benjamin and Stoker, Thomas and Suri, Tavneet, 2013). Also (Florida, Richard, 2014).

² According to a 2013 UN-Habitat report, “since 1990, 213 million slum dwellers have been added to the global population.” (UN-Habitat, 2105, p. 3).

³ “Both ‘poaching’ and fiscal bias, of course, are expressions of the poor majority’s lack of political clout throughout most of the Third World; urban democracy is still the exception rather than the rule, especially in Africa. ... A consensus of urban scholars agrees that public- and state-assisted housing in the Third World has primarily benefitted the urban middle class and elites, who expect to pay low taxes while receiving high levels of municipal services.” (Davis, 2006, p. 68-9)

⁴ “The practice of approaching services’ in an individualized, technocratic form highly reliant upon engineering solutions and expert knowledge reflects institutional and management overlaps and incoherencies between sectors that are not required or in the habit of communicating, whether across governmental ministries, departments or donors, and indeed, is valid across the services’ spectrum, whether for waste, water, food or energy. ... Approaches to municipal waster tend to be fairly technocratic in provision and analysis, ignoring the overlapping effects of waste on water, sanitation, food and health, with emphasis on the lack of political will and finances for operationalizing an effective waste management system, but one that does not explicitly address these interdependencies. Consequent to a lack of funds and communication strategies or data streaming between government agencies, waste disposal and management options have largely stagnated and failed to evolve to address new needs and waste forms.” (Thieme & Kovacs, 2015, p. 8-9)

⁵ “Particularly when it comes to basic service provision, a form of ‘malevolent urbanism’ has generated across urban areas in the global South, where unequal access to and use of the city is prevalent. At the same time, a mosaic of actors, sectors, and initiatives seek to address the ‘challenges of slums’, usually purporting to work *with* local communities, but often misunderstanding how everyday practices and expectations might differ from externally defined development goals and impact measures.” (Thieme & Kovacs, 2015, 1)